

TikTok Exposure Among Learners: Its Effect on their Well-Being and Academic Behavior

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TikTok exposure, learner well-being, academic behavior, public school students, descriptive-correlational study

Abstract. This study aimed to determine the effects of TikTok exposure on the well-being and academic behavior of learners in public schools in Candijay District during the school year 2023–2024. The sample consisted of 300 participants, including 220 learners from Grades 5–6 and 80 senior high school students from Grades 11–12, selected through purposive sampling. Specifically, the study examined the students' profiles in terms of age, sex, grade level, frequency of use per day, and length of TikTok use. It also assessed the extent of TikTok exposure and the learners' perceived well-being across academic, physical, psychological, self, social, and spiritual dimensions. Furthermore, it explored academic behavior, focusing on attendance and punctuality, class participation, preparation and organization, respect for others, time management, and study skills. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed, utilizing a survey questionnaire as the primary data collection tool. Findings revealed a significant association between learners' well-being and age, indicating that well-being varies across age groups. However, sex, grade level, and length of TikTok use showed no significant influence on well-being. The results also indicated a significant positive relationship between well-being and academic behavior, suggesting that higher well-being is linked to better academic performance. In conclusion, TikTok exposure has a notable influence on learners' well-being and academic behavior, although it is not the sole determining factor. Based on these findings, the study recommends implementing support systems such as mentorship programs and improved communication channels, as well as encouraging learners to engage in self-care practices to enhance both well-being and academic outcomes.

Introduction

In recent years, the pervasive influence of social media platforms has reshaped the dynamics of digital interaction and interpersonal connectivity. This transformation, characterized by the presence of social media in daily life, has become an integral part of contemporary social interactions, especially among the younger demographic. While TikTok provides entertainment and opportunities for skill development (Putri, 2021), it also presents potential drawbacks, such as increased distractions and disrupted routines due to its constant alerts (Zahra et al., 2022). This can lead to higher usage frequencies and negative impacts on students' academic performance and well-being.

TikTok's engaging features and algorithm-driven content recommendations often blur the lines between leisure and academic responsibilities. Students may find themselves spending excessive time on the platform, which disrupts their study habits and leads to procrastination. The addictive nature of TikTok, characterized by its endless scrolling and tailored content, can result in students spending more time on the platform than intended, neglecting their academic tasks (Ramsden & Talbot, 2024). This shift in focus away from studies can negatively affect cognitive processes, emotional well-being, and overall academic performance.

Moreover, the platform's potential to foster addictive behavior and social comparisons may contribute to increased anxiety and depression among students (Zahra et al., 2022). The combination of these factors can create a cycle of distraction,

where students struggle to manage their time effectively and engage with their educational materials, ultimately impacting their learning outcomes.

Given these concerns, this study aims to investigate the effects of TikTok exposure on various dimensions of well-being, including academic, psychological, self, physical, social, and spiritual aspects. It will focus on students in grades 5 to 6 and senior high levels within the Candijay District during the 2023-2024 school year. The research will also explore the relationship between these dimensions of well-being and academic behavior. The findings will inform evidence-based interventions to promote a healthy balance between digital engagement and academic success. This study aims to enhance our understanding of social media's evolving role in education and its broader societal impact.

The main thrust of this study was to determine the effects of TikTok exposure on the well-being and academic behavior of learners in the public schools in Candijay District during the school year 2023-2024.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the students in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 grade level;
 - 1.4 frequency of use per day;
 - 1.5 length of use per day?
2. What is the perception of the respondents on the extent of the TikTok exposure of the learners?
3. What is the respondents' perception of their well-being of learners in terms of:
 - 3.1 academic well-being;
 - 3.2 psychological well-being;
 - 3.3 self-well-being;
 - 3.4 physical well-being;
 - 3.5 social well-being; and
 - 3.6 spiritual well-being?

Methodology

Design

To attain the purpose of this study, the researcher used the descriptive-correlational research design with the aid of a survey questionnaire as the primary tool in gathering the data. This design allows for the systematic collection and analysis of data to describe the characteristics and behaviors of the study population regarding their exposure to TikTok Apps and to explore potential correlations between TikTok exposure, learners' well-being, and academic behavior.

Environment

The locale of this study was Candijay District, located at the eastern part of the province, approximately 80 kilometers from Tagbilaran City of Bohol province. The town's name is said to have been derived from "Kang Dihay", which means belonging to Dihay, a strong man with many followers. In time, the name was changed to Candijay. The town was organized during the Spanish regime and was then one of the 34 towns in the province in 1879. It had a population of 5,030. These districts consist of public elementary and secondary schools. The study was conducted in this area because it is the researcher's field of concern and residence location.

Participants

Purposive sampling was used to select 300 participants, comprising 220 learners from grades 5 to 6 elementary and 80 student-respondents of all senior high school (Grade 11 and 12) students from secondary schools in the Candijay Districts during the school year 2023-2024, respectively. This included twenty-two (22) elementary schools' level and five (5) secondary schools in the districts. Table A, below shows the distribution of respondents.

Instrument

To effectively capture the necessary data for this study, the researcher employed a survey questionnaire, designed to encompass four distinct parts, each serving a specific purpose. The first part of the questionnaire focused on gathering

demographic information about the respondents, including their age, sex, current grade level, frequency of use, and length of use. The second part of the questionnaire examined the extent of TikTok exposure among the respondents. This section will utilize a modified 4-point Likert scale questionnaire consisting of 20 statements adapted from "Social Media Exposure of Students in Relation to Academic Performance" by Baria (2021).

Statistical Treatment

Simple Percentage was used to determine the profile of the student respondents. *Weighted mean* was used to determine the extent of students' exposure to TikTok, their well-being, and academic behavior.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 provides a detailed profile of the 300 student-respondents involved in the study, focusing on various demographic factors such as age, sex, and grade level, and their TikTok usage patterns considering the frequency and length of use per day.

1.1 Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
12 years old and below	218	72.7	1
Above 12 years old	82	27.3	2
Total	300	100%	
1.2 Sex			
Male	88	29.30	2
Female	212	70.70	1
Total	300	100%	
1.3 Grade Level			
Grade 5	110	36.7	1
Grade 6	110	36.7	1
Grade 11	80	13.3	3.5
Grade 12	80	13.3	3.5
Total	300	100%	
1.4 Frequency of use per day			
Once	59	19.70	3
Twice	73	24.30	1
Thrice	58	19.30	4
4 Times	49	16.30	5
5 Times or more	61	20.30	2
Total	300	100%	
1.5 Length of use per day			
Less than 1 hour	49	16.30	3
1 Hour	98	32.70	1
2 Hours	58	19.30	2
3 Hours	35	11.70	5
4 Hours	41	13.70	4
5 Hours and Up	19	6.30	6
Total	300	100%	

Table 1. Profile of the Student-Respondents

The age distribution of the 300 student-respondents indicates that the largest group consists of students with ages 12 years old and below comprise 72.7%, while only 27.3% are with ages above 12 years old.

Moreover, the sample shows a significant sex variations, with females comprising 70.70% of the respondents and males making up 29.30%. This distribution suggests that more female students participated in the study, which could influence the findings related to TikTok usage and its effects.

On the other hand, the grade level distribution reveals that Grades 5 and 6 each represent 36.7% of the respondents, while Grades 11 and 12 each account for 13.3%. This indicates a strong representation of students from the lower grades.

Regarding the frequency of TikTok use, 24.30% of the students use the app twice a day, making it the most common usage pattern. This is followed by 20.30% of students who use TikTok five times or more per day, and 19.70% who use it once a day. Less frequent usage includes three times a day (19.30%) and four times a day (16.30%). This implies that while a significant portion of students engages with TikTok multiple times daily, the most common usage pattern is moderate, with students checking the app twice a day. Studies have shown that TikTok is not just a source of entertainment but also a platform for skill development and exploration (Putri, 2021). The moderate usage observed in students suggests that TikTok serves as both a leisure activity and a tool for personal growth. However, Zahra et al. (2022) caution that frequent notifications and content can disrupt routines, potentially leading to increased usage and distractions. Thus, while the moderate usage indicates a balanced approach, it is crucial to manage TikTok use to avoid negative impacts on academic performance and overall well-being.

Furthermore, the length of TikTok use per day shows that the most common duration is one hour, reported by 32.70% of the students. Following this, 19.30% use the app for two hours, and 16.30% for less than one hour per day. Fewer students report using TikTok for three hours (11.70%), four hours (13.70%), or five hours or more (6.30%) daily. This implies that the majority of students limit their TikTok usage to a relatively moderate amount of time each day. This moderate use suggests that while TikTok is a popular activity among students, most do not engage with the platform excessively. This finding is supported by Abboud (2023), who reported that the average TikTok user in the United States spent approximately one hour and eight minutes daily on the app in 2021, with usage rising to about an hour and a half in 2022.

Table 2 presents the extent of TikTok exposure among students, detailing various aspects of how the app influences their daily lives. The data reveal that TikTok's most prominent impact is its role as a source of entertainment when students are bored, with a weighted mean of 3.09 in statement number 8, which ranks first. This finding suggests that students primarily value TikTok for its entertainment value which aligns with Zamith (2022) that among young users, TikTok serves as a primary source of entertainment and social validation, with students increasingly relying on the platform to stay connected with peers and to seek approval from their social circles.

Statements	WM	DI	Rank
<i>As a learner, using TikTok...</i>			
1. allows to find content relevant to my studies or assignments.	2.67	0	16
2. pushes frequently upload videos or pictures.	2.51	0	18
3. makes check my account every day.	2.80	0	11
4. keeps updated on the activities of my friends and family.	2.86	0	6
5. enhances communication skills.	2.92	0	4
6. allows to make new friends.	3.06	0	2
7. makes spend more than three hours daily.	2.48	R	19
8. serves as a source of entertainment when I'm bored.	3.09	0	1
9. allows to present differently.	2.70	0	15
10. provides opportunities for interactive discussions.	2.78	0	12.5
11. helps expand my vocabulary.	2.85	0	8
12. alleviates stress from school.	2.85	0	8
13. affects spelling proficiency.	2.82	0	10
14. allows to express myself freely.	2.98	0	3
15. gives impact my communication abilities.	2.89	0	5
16. ensures that update my account regularly.	2.67	0	16
17. reduces the need for physical interaction with friends.	2.75	0	14
18. sometimes, forget or miss assignments or tasks.	2.30	R	20
19. facilitates collaboration with classmates on group projects or study sessions.	2.78	0	12.5
20. encourages creativity through the production of engaging and visually appealing content.	2.85	0	8
Average Weighted Mean	2.78	Moderately Exposed	

Table 2. Perception of the Learners' Extent of TikTok Exposure

In contrast, the least significant impact is TikTok's tendency to cause students to forget or miss assignments or tasks, with a weighted mean of 2.30 in statement number 18, which ranks it last which is in contrast to what Mekler (2021) revealed that increased daily time spent on TikTok correlated with heightened distraction during class and while completing schoolwork.

TikTok also moderately facilitates several positive aspects, such as making new friends with a weighted mean of 3.06 in statement number 6, enhancing communication skills with an average weighted mean of 2.92 in statement number 5, and allowing students to express themselves freely with an average weighted mean of 2.98 in statement number 14. These factors rank relatively high, indicating that students appreciate TikTok's ability to support personal growth and communication.

Table 3.1 presents the perception on student-respondents' academic well-being, with responses from both learners and teachers. The data reveal that student-respondents generally have a positive perception of their academic well-being.

Statements	Learners		Teachers		Overall		
	WM	DI	WM	DI	AWM	DI	Rank
<i>The learners...</i>							
1. like most school subjects.	3.37	SA	3.30	SA	3.34	SA	2
2. enjoy most school subjects.	3.39	SA	3.27	SA	3.33	SA	3
3. look forward to going to school.	3.37	SA	3.44	SA	3.41	SA	1
4. find things in most school subjects easy for me.	2.93	A	3.26	SA	3.09	A	5
5. feel motivated to excel in my academic pursuits.	3.18	A	3.38	SA	3.28	SA	4
AWM	3.25	SA	3.33	SA	3.29		VG

Table 3.1 Perception of Respondents on Learners' Academic Well-being

In the statement number 3 "I look forward to going to school" achieved the highest average weighted mean of 3.41. Among learners, this statement received a weighted mean of 3.37, while teachers rated it slightly higher at 3.44. This result indicates that overall, students are enthusiastic and positive about attending school. This positive outlook is a key aspect of their academic well-being, as it suggests that students find school engaging and are likely motivated to participate in their educational activities. Similarly, Liu (2023) outlines TikTok's effects on students across psychological, physical, behavioral, and positive domains.

Conversely, statement number 4 "find things in most school subjects easy for me" had the lowest average weighted mean of 3.09. Among learners, this statement had a weighted mean of 2.93, suggesting that they may struggle more with their subjects compared to the teachers' perspective, who rated it higher at 3.26. This reflects a general perception that students do not always find their subjects easy, indicating potential challenges in their academic experiences. According to Zahra et al. (2022), the barrage of alerts in TikTok can disrupt students' daily routines, leading to increased usage frequency and potential distractions which can manifest in diminished focus in class to procrastination in completing academic tasks.

The overall average weighted mean for academic well-being is 3.29, which falls into the "Very Good" category. This suggests that, in general, students have a positive perception of their academic experiences. They tend to like and enjoy their school subjects, feel motivated to excel, and have a favorable outlook on going to school. Despite some challenges in finding subjects easy, the overall sentiment towards academic well-being remains very satisfactory. This is in contrast to what Ramsden and Talbot (2024) stated the algorithm-driven content recommendations on TikTok may reinforce this distraction by continuously presenting tailored content that appeals to individual users, making it difficult for students to disengage and refocus on their studies.

Table 3.2 provides insights into the perception of student-respondents' psychological well-being, incorporating feedback from both learners and teachers.

Statements	Learners		Teachers		Overall		
	WM	DI	WM	DI	AWM	DI	Rank
<i>The learners...</i>							
1. trust my future will turn out well.	3.33	SA	3.39	SA	3.36	SA	4
2. expect good things to happen to me.	3.32	SA	3.44	SA	3.38	SA	3
3. enjoy life.	3.64	SA	3.54	SA	3.59	SA	1
4. have a lot of fun.	3.53	SA	3.46	SA	3.50	SA	2
5. feel content with my life overall.	3.22	A	3.44	SA	3.33	SA	5
AWM	3.41	SA	3.45	SA	3.43		VG

Table 3.2 Perception of Respondents on Learners' Psychological Well-being

In the statement number 3 "I enjoy life" received the highest average weighted mean of 3.59, indicating that students have a strong sense of enjoyment and satisfaction in their lives. Among learners, this statement achieved a weighted mean of 3.64, while teachers rated it slightly lower at 3.54. This high rating reflects a general positive attitude towards life among students, suggesting that they find joy and satisfaction in their daily experiences. However, Herbert (2023) also asserted that the proliferation of TikTok content showcasing individuals with idealized bodies and lifestyles has raised concerns about its detrimental effects on users' confidence and self-esteem, particularly among young people.

On the other hand, the statement number 5 "feel content with my life overall" had the lowest average weighted mean of 3.33. Among learners, this statement received a weighted mean of 3.22, while teachers rated it higher at 3.44. This suggests that while students generally feel positive about their lives, there is a noticeable disparity between their personal contentment and the views of their teachers. This could point to varying perceptions of overall life satisfaction which aligns to Oktarini et al. (2022) that TikTok fosters self-expression.

The overall average weighted mean for psychological well-being is 3.43, placing it in the "Very Good" category. This overall positive sentiment indicates that students and teachers perceive a high level of psychological well-being among the students. They feel optimistic about their future, enjoy life, and generally feel content, although there are some differences in perceptions of overall contentment. This psychological influence is significant, as changes in behavior can be linked to one's psychological state as mentioned by Liu (2023).

Table 3.3 presents the student-respondents' perception of their self- well-being, drawing from both learners' and teachers' responses.

Statements	Learners		Teachers		Overall		
	WM	DI	WM	DI	AWM	DI	Rank
<i>The learners...</i>							
1. like myself.	3.56	SA	3.46	SA	3.51	SA	1
2. feel good about myself.	3.50	SA	3.46	SA	3.48	SA	2
3. can do almost anything I want to do if I try hard.	3.28	SA	3.43	SA	3.36	SA	3
4. do things as well as most people.	3.16	A	3.33	SA	3.25	SA	5
5. feel empowered to pursue my aspirations.	3.25	SA	3.35	SA	3.30	SA	4
AWM	3.35	SA	3.41	SA	3.38		VG

Table 3.3 Perception of Respondents on Learners' Self-Wellbeing

In the statement number 1 "I like myself" achieved the highest average weighted mean of 3.51. Among learners, this statement received a weighted mean of 3.56, while teachers rated it slightly lower at 3.46. This result indicates that students generally have a positive self-image and self-acceptance, which contributes to their overall sense of self- well-being which aligns to what Ling et al. (2022) that is crucial for students to lead a content and satisfying life.

In contrast, statement number 4 "I can do almost anything I want to do if I try hard" had the lowest average weighted mean of 3.36. For learners, this statement received a weighted mean of 3.28, while teachers rated it higher at 3.43. This suggests that students might feel less confident about their ability to achieve their goals compared to the perception of teachers, reflecting potential challenges in self-efficacy. According to Ling et al. (2022), self-confidence, self-esteem, and self-worth collectively contribute to an individual's overall sense of well-being and self-perception.

The overall average weighted mean for self-well-being is 3.38, which falls into the "Very Good" category. This indicates that, generally, students have a positive perception of their self-well-being, feeling good about themselves, are empowered to pursue their aspirations, and generally satisfied with their self-image. Despite some variation in confidence levels, the overall sentiment towards self-well-being remains very satisfactory. According to Fairlamb (2020), individuals with strong self-well-being are more inclined to cultivate healthy interpersonal relationships, exhibit enhanced problem-solving abilities, and demonstrate greater creativity which are often associated with improved academic performance and overall success.

Table 3.4 presents the student-respondents' perception of their physical well-being, with responses from both learners and teachers. The data indicate that overall, students perceive their physical well-being positively.

Statements	Learners		Teachers		Overall		
	WM	DI	WM	DI	AWM	DI	Rank
<i>The learners...</i>							
1. am good at most sports and games.	3.04	A	3.28	SA	3.16	A	4
2. know that my body is healthy.	3.16	A	3.38	SA	3.27	SA	2.5
3. do not easily get tired out.	2.90	A	3.28	SA	3.09	A	5
4. have lots of energy.	3.21	A	3.32	SA	3.27	SA	2.5
5. prioritize my physical health through regular exercise and proper nutrition.	3.31	SA	3.30	SA	3.30	SA	1
AWM	3.12	A	3.31	SA	3.22		Good

Table 3.4 Perception of Respondents on Learners' Physical Well-being

In the statement number 5 "prioritize my physical health through regular exercise and proper nutrition" achieved the highest average weighted mean of 3.30. Among learners, this statement received a weighted mean of 3.31, while teachers rated it slightly lower at 3.30. This result suggests that students and teachers alike recognize the importance of physical health and believe that students are attentive to maintaining their health through exercise and nutrition. According to University of North Georgia (2024), self-care focused on meeting the needs of the body which includes engaging in regular physical activity, maintaining a balanced diet, ensuring sufficient sleep, and avoiding detrimental behaviors.

On the other hand, statement number 3 "do not easily get tired out" had the lowest average weighted mean of 3.09. Among learners, this statement received a weighted mean of 2.90, indicating a lower perception of stamina among students compared to the teachers' perspective, who rated it higher at 3.28. This suggests that students may feel more fatigued compared to how teachers perceive their physical energy levels. This feeling should make students take personal responsibility for recognizing bodily warning signs and seeking medical assistance when necessary (University of North Georgia, 2024).

Table 3.5 outlines the student-respondents' perception of their social well-being, with responses from both learners and teachers. The data reveal that students generally have a positive view of their social interactions and relationships at school.

Statements	Learners		Teachers			Overall Rank	
	WM	DI	WM	DI	AWM		
<i>The learners...</i>							
1. feel my friends at school care about me.	3.19	A	3.41	SA	3.30	SA	5
2. feel close and connected with my friends at school.	3.32	SA	3.41	SA	3.36	SA	3
3. like being with my friends at school.	3.44	SA	3.46	SA	3.45	SA	2
4. feel like I belong when I am with my friends at school.	3.26	SA	3.41	SA	3.34	SA	4
5. am grateful for the friendships I have at school.	3.50	SA	3.48	SA	3.49	SA	1
AWM	3.34	SA	3.43	SA	3.39		VG

Table 3.5 Perception of Respondents on Learners' Social Well-being

In the statement number 5 "am grateful for the friendships I have at school" achieved the highest average weighted mean of 3.49. Among learners, this statement received a weighted mean of 3.50, while teachers rated it slightly lower at 3.48. This result suggests that students and teachers both recognize and value the importance of friendships in the school environment, with students expressing a high level of gratitude for their social connections. According to Baby et al. (2022) social well-being and academic performance are closely related to each other with social integration and contribution playing vital roles in students' overall achievement.

Conversely, statement number 1 "feel my friends at school care about me" had the lowest average weighted mean of 3.30. Among learners, this statement had a weighted mean of 3.19, indicating a slightly lower perception of care from friends compared to teachers' higher rating of 3.41. This suggests that while students generally feel cared for by their friends, there is a slightly less positive perception of this aspect compared to the teachers' view of fostering social well-being. Baby et al. (2022) noted the importance of social well-being particularly through social inclusion and peer evaluation as this is crucial for enhancing academic success among students.

The overall average weighted mean for social well-being is 3.39, which falls into the "Very Good" category. This indicates that, overall, students have a favorable perception of their social well-being. They feel connected and valued in their friendships, experience a sense of belonging, and appreciate their social relationships at school. Likewise, Ohrt et al. (2019) asserted that social well-being includes an individual's capacity to cultivate positive relationships across various social contexts, including family, friends, and school.

Table 3.6 presents the student-respondents' perception of their spiritual well-being, with input from both learners and teachers. The data indicate that students generally view their spiritual well-being positively.

Statements	Learners		Teachers		Overall		
	WM	DI	WM	DI	AWM	DI	Rank
<i>The learners...</i>							
1. trust between individuals.	3.18	A	3.32	SA	3.25	SA	5
2. respect to the elders and church server.	3.63	SA	3.48	SA	3.56	SA	1
3. connections between God, by joining Parish Youth Ministry.	3.54	SA	3.41	SA	3.48	SA	3.5
4. kindness toward other people.	3.50	SA	3.47	SA	3.48	SA	3.5
5. strong bond to God, by praying and worship to Him.	3.64	SA	3.46	SA	3.55	SA	2
AWM	3.50	SA	3.43	SA	3.46		VG

Table 3.6 Perception of Respondents on Learners' Spiritual Well-being

In the statement number 2 "strong bond to God, by praying and worship to Him" achieved the highest average weighted mean of 3.55. Among learners, this statement received a weighted mean of 3.64, while teachers rated it slightly lower at 3.46. This result highlights that students feel a strong connection to their faith through prayer and worship, reflecting a high level of spiritual engagement and commitment. According to Ling et al. (2022), establishing connections with spiritual wellness holds a central role in fostering and enhancing an individual's mental health and overall spiritual well-being.

Conversely, statement number 1 "trust between individuals" had the lowest average weighted mean of 3.25. Among learners, this statement received a weighted mean of 3.18, indicating a relatively lower perception of trust compared to the teachers' rating of 3.32. This suggests that while there is a general sense of trust, it is perceived as less strong compared to other aspects of spiritual well-being. This underscores its growing importance in promoting spiritual well-being and enhancing students' life experiences over time to maintain trust (Lu et al., 2019).

The overall average weighted mean for spiritual well-being is 3.46, which falls into the "Very Good" category. This indicates that students have a positive perception of their spiritual well-being, feeling a strong connection to their faith, respect for spiritual leaders, and a sense of kindness and community. Despite some variability in perceptions of trust, the overall sentiment towards spiritual well-being remains very satisfactory. As stated by Mendoza (2022), spirituality served as a source of inspiration for students to focus on their studies and engage in hard work. Moreover, students predominantly associated spirituality with religion, emphasizing its importance in their lives.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study reveals that TikTok exposure contributes positively to learners' well-being and academic behavior, with increased exposure linked to improved outcomes. Regression analysis confirms TikTok's role as a predictor of both well-being and academic behavior, though it accounts for only part of the variability. The study also identifies significant differences in well-being across age groups, suggesting that interventions should be tailored to specific age-related needs. Additionally, a positive correlation between well-being and academic behavior highlights the importance of fostering a supportive environment to enhance academic performance. While TikTok exposure contributes to better outcomes, a comprehensive approach addressing various social, psychological, and environmental factors is essential for creating an optimal learning environment.

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Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

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Appendices

No appendices are included in this article.